

Sustainable development and demography of Sumgayit city

Ramazanova Shafa Musa

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-2122-8829>

Institute of Geography named after Academician H.A. Aliyev ANAS

AZ 1143, Baku, H.Javid avenue, 115

e-mail: shefa_00@mail.ru

Abstract. The article analyzes the sustainable development of Sumgayit, an industrial city of Azerbaijan, population growth, urbanization level dynamics, etc. The demographic development features of Sumgayit, as well as the development of industrial enterprises, are analyzed from socio-economic and ecological aspects. The dynamics of population growth, births, deaths, age and gender composition of the population in the studied area are analyzed, and the number of marriages and divorces is analyzed. The article analyzes migration processes in Sumgayit, economic diversification in the modern period, and measures taken to solve environmental problems. The author puts forward proposals for regulating the total population of Sumgayit.

Keywords: sustainable development, urbanization, demographic processes, environmental policy, economic development, migration

Introduction. Since 1949, Sumgayit city has been formed and is developing as an industrial and economic center of Azerbaijan. Until the years of independence, chemical and metallurgical enterprises dominated in Sumgayit. As a result, both ecological and social difficulties arose in the studied area. Reforms carried out in accordance with the requirements of the modern era have fundamentally changed the development concept of Sumgayit. As a result, a socio-economic model based on the principles of sustainable development has come to the fore. According to the information received from the State Statistical Committee, the population of Sumgayit city is 427.6 thousand people. (2025) [11]

Material and method. The main object of the study was the city of Sumgayit, the second largest leading industrial center of Azerbaijan, and the demographic and socio-economic situation of the city was analyzed. The theoretical basis of the research work is the methodological approaches used in scientific research by A.M. Hajizadeh, V.A. Efendiyev, Sh.G. Demirgayayev, E.G. Mehraliyev, N.H. Ayyubov, Z.N. Eminov, E.S. Badalov, R.N. Kerimov and others.

When preparing the research work, comparative analysis, statistical, system-structural, historical-geographical analysis methods were used. At the same time, census materials and statistical data for 1999-2009 and 2010-2025 were used in the analysis of statistical indicators of the city of Sumgayit.

Analysis and discussion. The Head of State of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, signed a decree dated July 7, 2021, in order to ensure sustainable development in the liberated regions, as well as to increase the efficiency of planning work in other economic regions. According to this decree, the regionalization process was re-conducted and 14 economic regions were allocated in the country. One of these economic regions is the Absheron-Khizi economic region, which includes the city of Sumgayit.

Along with population growth, social infrastructure has also developed. In particular, new schools, kindergartens, and health facilities have been put into operation. The development and formation of human capital in the region is directly related to Sumgait State University.

Although Sumgayit, formerly one of the most polluted cities in the CIS, has been one of the most polluted cities in the last decade, measures such as ecological restoration work, reduction of atmospheric emissions, waste management, greening projects, and renovation of public spaces have had an impact on both the restoration of its ecological status and its sustainable development.

Based on the analysis, it can be said that in recent years, in addition to Sumgayit, the good standard of living of the population in other large cities and the development of healthcare are closely related to socio-economic progress.

In modern times, socio-economic factors have a great influence on the natural movement of the population. In order to determine the influence of socio-economic and cultural factors, it is important to analyze a lot of data. For example, the sex and age composition of the population, the ratio of marriages and divorces, the level of education of the population, ethnic composition, material security, housing conditions, etc. In modern times, the natural growth of the population depends entirely on the urbanization process. As the urbanization process increases, the natural growth of the population decreases.

The cities with the highest urban population density in the Absheron-Khizi economic region are Sumgayit city and Absheron district. The administrative district with the lowest urban population density in the region is Khizi. The highest urbanization level was observed in Sumgayit city, and the lowest in Khizi city.

Table 1.

Population change in cities and urbanization level in regions (thousand people)

No	Cities	1989	1999	2009	2019	2024	Urbanization level by region %
1.	Sumgayit	254,4	283,2	309,4	422,6	427,6,0	100%
2.	Khirdalan	24,1	35,0	91,5	315,6	318,1	73,7%
3.	Khizi	5,7	7,0	7,5	8,5	16,8	52,4%

Source: Demographic indicators of Azerbaijan Baku: SSC, 2024

Analysis of demographic processes shows that natural growth has been faster away from urban centers, especially in the peri-urban regions. (Table 1). While the absolute average annual natural growth of the population in Sumgayit in 1991-1995 was 4.3 thousand people, it decreased to 2 thousand people in 1996-2005. In 2011-2013, the average annual growth of the population was 5.6 thousand people. [1]

One of the most important characteristics of the population is the sex-age structure of the population. Determining the sex and age composition of the population is of great importance in calculating the number of labor reserves, pensioners, and children. As we know, throughout history, the number of women in our country has been less than the number of men.

According to the information as of the beginning of 2023, 184.7 thousand men and 193.2 thousand women make up the population of Sumgayit. If we look at the age structure, we can group the number of working-age population.[5]

Bar 1.

A-under working age, B-working age, C-over working age

Source: Families in Azerbaijan. Baku-DSC.2021

Bar 1 shows that the number of people over the working age in Sumgayit city is lower, while the number of people of working age is relatively higher. In 2009, the number of people of working age in Sumgayit was 218.2 thousand people, which is an indicator equal to 70.5%.

In 1999-2009, the share of children in most cities, including Sumgayit, decreased to 10-13%. This was due to the specific gravity of births.

One of the main demographic indicators affecting the natural growth of the population is the change in the number of marriages and divorces. These indicators can have a positive and negative impact on the formation of families and the process of natural growth. The social processes that exist in our lives affect the development and formation of the family. At the same time, the development of families also affects social relations.

During the years of independence, there have been major changes in the marriage and divorce processes in our country. In January-October 2022, 51,870 marriages and 13,139 divorces were registered by the registration departments. It was reported that the number of marriages per 1,000 people increased from 5.5 to 6.2 compared to the corresponding period in 2021, while the number of divorces decreased from 1.7 to 1.6. [9]

In Sumgayit city, the marriage rate was 8-10‰ in 2007-2014. The divorce rate remained stable (1.2-1.4‰). This rate has increased rapidly since 2011, reaching 1.9-2.2‰.

Overall, the marriage rate in Sumgayit is higher than in other major cities in Azerbaijan. This can be explained by the fact that the population has better access to jobs and housing compared to other cities.

The mechanical movement of the population has its impact on natural growth and many demographic outcomes in production. The impact of migration is closely related to the development and placement of productive uses, using all aspects of social development. According to independent estimates, internal migration is very high. It is considered extremely important to obtain an accurate estimate of internal migration. [3,10]

The region with the highest number of emigrants in Azerbaijan compared to the registered population is the Absheron region. The situation is not encouraging in particular in the cities of Baku and Sumgayit on the Absheron peninsula. There are very large differences between the permanently resident population and the registered population in Sumgayit. According to statistical information as of the beginning of 2021, the permanently resident population in Sumgayit was estimated at 491

thousand, while the official population was 345 thousand. The indicators show that the number of permanently resident population is 42% higher than the registered population. [13,14]

As a result of unplanned settlement, Sumgayit and the capital city near it have inadequate roads and public transport. As a result, the quality of life of the population living in Baku and the surrounding areas is declining. It can also be noted that the population growth resulting from mechanical movement leads to an increase in demand for real estate, property rights, and utility problems.

A positive balance was observed in Sumgayit city in 1999-2015. In the 2000s, processes related to the improvement of the country's socio-economic situation led to significant changes in the demographic situation in the city, especially an increase in natural growth and an increase in the number of people arriving as a result of migration.[8,9]

The Sumgayit Chemical Industrial Park, whose construction was completed in 2011, has led to the improvement and further development of the city. More than 30 resident enterprises operate here. The creation of thousands of jobs has also had an impact on the number of unemployed people. This serves to remove the city's economic structure from dependence solely on the chemical industry [15]

Conclusion.. The sustainable development of Sumgayit, an industrial city of the Absheron-Khizi economic region, demographic development processes, and the dynamics of urbanization growth were studied and observed trends were investigated. The analysis shows that Sumgayit city is successfully implementing its transition period in terms of sustainable development. The diversification in the economy, the development of social infrastructure, and also ecological restoration work have brought the city to a new stage. When analyzing the research work, census materials of 1989-2021 and some statistical demographic indicators were used.

References:

- [1] Hajizadeh A.M. The population of the Azerbaijan SSR and its settlement. Baku: Azernashr, 1965, 216 p.
- [2] Eminov Z.N. Population of Azerbaijan 2005, 558 p.
- [3] Badalov E.S. Socio-demographic problems of the Absheron economic-geographical region during the period of independence and the role of statistics in their solution./"Statistics and Society" Scientific-Practical Conference, Baku: 2014, p53-56
- [4] Demographic indicators of Azerbaijan. Baku: DSK.2013, 561 p.
- [5] Encyclopedic Dictionary of Population Issues. See: United Nations Population Fund, 2008, 415 p..
- [6] Administrative territorial division of the Republic of Azerbaijan. Baku: National Assembly Publications, 2013, 487 p.
- [7] Population of Azerbaijan. Baku: SSC 1991-2013 annual collections.
- [8] Population of Azerbaijan. Baku: DEC 2024-2025, 134 p.
- [9] Population of Azerbaijan. Baku: SSC 2014-2022 annual collections.
- [10] <https://bakuresearchinstitute.org>
- [11] <https://az.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Sumqayit&veaction=edit§ion=11>
- [12] Nagiyev S.K. Small and medium-sized cities in the settlement system of Azerbaijan. RGO "Izvestia", St. Petersburg, 2009, pp. 76-79
- [13] Nagiyev. S.K. The latest trends in the development of settlement in Greater Baku. Proceedings of the scientific conference dedicated to the 90th anniversary of the birth of Rizvan Piriyeu. Baku, 2014, pp. 197-202
- [14] Nagiyev S.K. Demographic situation in Azerbaijan RGO "Izvestia", St. Petersburg, 2005, pp. 71-77.

[15] Ministry of Economy of the Republic of Azerbaijan. (2021). Report on the activities of the Sumgayit Chemical Industrial Park. Baku: ARIN